

Professional Quality of Elementary School Teachers of Alipurduar District in West Bengal

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Abstract—Teacher professional quality plays a significance role in dealing with academic and administrative work of an institution. In this study researcher aims to discuss the professional quality of male and female teacher in relation to demographic factor i.e. gender, locale and Teaching Experience. Those factors have important implication to understand and evaluate teacher's professional quality. T-test and ANOVA were used to analysis the data. A sample of 200 teacher's comprising 110 male and 90 female. Overall male and female elementary school teacher in Alipurduar district of West Bengal exhibited no significance difference on their professional quality. However, difference was found in respect to teaching experience. The study concludes that since the quality of education being delivered, generally has been considered as a function of teachers. There is a need for both substantive and methodological focus on professional development course based on teaching experience in order to take out maximum outcome from male and female teacher to reduce high degree of professionalism in their respective work place.

Keywords: Professional Quality, Primary School Teachers, Teaching Experience, Alipurduar

I. INTRODUCTION

In present global educational landscape, the role of school is increasingly expected to showcase their educational strength. Teacher professional quality serving as the cornerstone of the educational process. This has become significant especially due to recent advancement in educational policy. NEP-2020 give important to school education and quality of the teacher. The role of a teacher in shaping the educational experience of student is undeniably vital. An educational system can only progress as far as its teachers' capabilities. Teachers play a pivotal role in building a knowledgeable and thriving society. The quality of primary school teachers plays a pivotal role in shaping the educational experiences and outcomes of young learners. As the foundation of formal education, primary schooling not only imparts fundamental academic skills but also nurtures cognitive, social, and emotional development. According to Darling-Hammond (2000), the effectiveness of this stage largely depends on the professional quality of teachers, which encompasses their pedagogical competencies, subject knowledge, classroom management skills, and commitment to continuous professional development. Professional quality in primary school teaching is a multifaceted construct influenced by various factors, including teacher education, training, experience, and motivation. Shulman (1987) emphasizes that well-trained and highly skilled teachers significantly impact student achievement, engagement, and overall learning progress. Moreover, Hattie (2009) highlights that professional attribute such as adaptability, empathy, and a reflective approach to teaching contribute to a dynamic and responsive learning environment.

This study explores the concept of professional quality among primary school teachers, examining key determinants and their implications for student learning. By analysing empirical studies and theoretical perspectives, this research aims to identify best practices in teacher education and professional development that can enhance teaching effectiveness in primary schools. As noted by Cochran-Smith and Lytle (1999), improving teacher preparation and continuous professional learning are essential for enhancing educational quality. The findings of this study will contribute to ongoing discussions on educational quality and inform policies aimed at strengthening the professional standards of primary educators.

I.I. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

The professional quality of primary school teachers is vital for effective teaching and student development. This study is based on key educational theories. Shulman's (1986) Pedagogical Content Knowledge (PCK) Theory emphasizes both content expertise and effective subject delivery. Vygotsky's (1978) Socio-Cultural Theory highlights the role of social interactions in learning, while Maslow's (1943) Hierarchy of Needs stresses addressing students' holistic needs for optimal learning. The study adopts a multi-dimensional framework, including professional knowledge, instructional competence, communication skills, ethical commitment, and adaptability. Empirical research by Darling-Hammond (2000) and Hattie (2009) confirms the strong correlation between teacher quality and student achievement. This framework supports the development of the Teacher Competency Scale, integrating pedagogical theories and empirical evidence to assess primary school teachers in Alipurduar and their impact on education.

I.II. OBJECTIVES

The primary objectives of this study are:

1. To assess the overall Professional Quality levels of primary school teachers in Alipurduar district in West Bengal.
2. To examine the difference of demographic factors such as Sex, Area, teaching experience.
3. To examine the influence of teaching experience on professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District in West Bengal.
4. To provide recommendations for teacher training programs and policy interventions to enhance Professional Quality.

I.III. HYPOTHESES

H₀₁ There is no significance difference between the professional quality of Male and Female elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District of West Bengal.

H₀₂ There is no significance difference of professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District of West Bengal across sex and locale.

H₀₃ There is no significance difference of demographic factors such as Sex, Area, teaching experience among elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District of West Bengal.

H₀₄ There is no significance influence of teaching experience on professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District of West Bengal.

III. METHODOLOGY

The present study is descriptive in nature. The target population of the study comprised of elementary school teachers from Alipurduar district of West Bengal. A sample of 200 elementary school teachers including 110 (55%) males and 90 (45%) females working in 60 different primary schools was drawn from the target population by random sampling technique. The participants had 1 to 31 years of teaching experience in schools.

The professional Quality variable was determined by Likert five-point (Always, Often, Sometimes, Rarely and Never) Teacher Professional Quality Scale (TPQS) which was self-constructed and standardized. The scale contained 60 items aimed to evaluate teachers' professional Quality in the dimensions of rules and regulations for teachers, Planning and Preparation of Organizational Work and, Mastery over the Understanding Teaching Techniques. The English versions of the Scale were administered along with explanation of the purpose of the survey and detailed instructions to fill up the scale. Before being used in a pilot study the tool was revised several times with the help of experts to find out whether there was a need to modify, add or delete some items. Each teacher was to respond by putting tick mark in appropriate boxes given against the items with which the teacher agreed. There was no option to leave any item unanswered. The lower scores on the teacher professional quality scale indicated ineffective teachers and vice versa. The Scale was distributed to the teachers of elementary level in different schools after the

approval of School Inspector (SI), District Inspector (DI) of Alipurduar District. The subjects of the study were introduced with objectives of the study and requested to read the instructions carefully and ask the researcher if there was any difficulty in understanding the instructions. It was emphasized that no item should be omitted and that there were no correct or incorrect answers. There was no time limit for the scale to fill-up. The raw scores as obtained directly abstracted from the booklets. In order to make meaningful interpretation and draw conclusions raw scores were reorganized appropriately statistical analysis and summarization. This was achieved by using the statistical package of SPSS version 26.0. In preliminary analysis, the internal consistency of the scale was examined. The final statements were selected after item analysis and internal consistency.

An alpha level of 0.05 was established for determining statistical significance. Each item was assigned a weightage ranging from 5 (Always) to 1 (Never) for Positive items. In case of Negative items, the scoring was reversed, i.e. from 1 (Always) to 5 (Never). The professional quality score of an individual teacher is the sum total of item scores on all the three areas. The range of possible scores is from 60 to 300 with the higher score indicating the more professional Quality and vice versa. Cronbach's alpha of 0.990 was obtained for TPQS. The analysis of the research t-test and ANOVA were employed to evaluate the impact of teaching experience on professional quality score. ANOVA was followed by where F -value was found to be significant so as to identify the trend of the difference in mean values.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Objective-1: To assess the overall Professional Quality levels of primary school teachers in Alipurduar district in West Bengal.

Table-1

Overall levels of Professional Quality of elementary School Teachers

Range of z-Score	Range of RAW Score	Professional Quality Level	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Below -2σ	Below 155	Very Low Professional Quality	0	0%
From -2σ to 1σ	From 156 to 190	Low Professional Quality	6	3%
From -1σ to $+1\sigma$	From 191 to 258	Moderate Professional Quality	78	39%
From $+1\sigma$ to 2σ	From 259 to 293	High Professional Quality	107	53.5%
Above $+2\sigma$	Above 294	Very High Professional Quality	9	4.5%
Total			200	100

The analysis presented in Table-1 shows the Professional Quality of Elementary School Teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal. The result show that a substantial proportion of teachers demonstrate high professional quality, with the majority falling within the moderate to high level of professional quality. Teachers in the Alipurduar district display commendable levels of professional quality. The presence of a considerable percentage of teachers in the high and very high professional quality level reflects a high level of professional commitment, instructional effectiveness and adherence to professional norms. Conversely, only a small proportion of teachers fall into the low professional quality level. This indicating that very few teachers exhibit low professional quality. Overall, the findings suggest that the elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district possess a high professional quality. Hence, the hypothesis stating that ‘There is no significance difference between the professional quality of Male and Female elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District of West Bengal’ is retained.

Table-2

Levels of professional quality of elementary school teachers based on Sex and Locale

Professional Quality Level	Male (N=110)	Female (N=90)	Urban (N=90)	Rural (N=110)
Very Low Professional Quality	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)	0(0%)
Low Professional Quality	4(3.64%)	2(2.22%)	1(1.11%)	5(4.55%)
Moderate Professional Quality	43(39.09%)	35(38.89%)	35(38.89%)	43(39.09%)
High Professional Quality	60(54.55%)	47(52.22%)	51(56.67%)	56(50.91%)
Very High Professional Quality	3(2.73%)	6(6.67%)	3(3.33%)	6(5.45%)
Total	110(100%)	90(100%)	90(100%)	110(100%)

The analysis presented in Table-2 show the Professional Quality levels among elementary school teachers in Alipurduar district of West Bengal across sex and locale. The findings show that both male and female teachers demonstrate strong professional quality, as none of the teachers fall into the very low professional quality level. Among male teachers, 54.55% exhibit high professional quality, followed by 39.09% with moderate and 2.73% with very high professional quality. Similarly, female teachers also show favourable professional quality, with 52.22% in the high level, 38.89% in the moderate level, and a slightly higher percentage (6.67%) in the very high professional quality range compared to males. When analysed by locale, teachers from both urban and rural areas show comparable levels of professional quality. In urban areas, 56.67% of teachers fall in the high professional quality level and 3.33% in the very high level. While 38.89% exhibit moderate professional quality. Rural teachers also reflect similar professional quality, with 50.91% showing high and 5.45% showing very high professional quality, alongside 39.09% exhibiting moderate levels. Overall, the results show that professional quality remains consistently strong irrespective of sex and locale. Hence, the hypothesis stating that ‘There is no significance difference of professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District of West Bengal across sex and locale’ is retained.

Objective-2: To examine the difference of professional quality based on demographic factors such as Sex, Area.

Table-3

Mean difference between Total Professional Quality Score of Male and Female elementary school Teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal.

Gender	N	MEAN	SD	SEM	df	t	p-value
Male	110	259.80	26.128	2.491			
Female	90	259.59	24.710	2.605	198	0.258	0.890
Total	200						

Note. level of significance 0.05.

The results presented in Table-3 show the comparison of total Professional Quality scores between male and female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District. The mean Professional Quality score for male teachers is almost identical to that of female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar in West Bengal. The result show that there is no statistically significant difference in the professional quality of male and female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal. Thus, both male and female teachers demonstrate similar levels of professional quality. Hence, the hypothesis stating that ‘There is no significance

difference of professional quality based on demographic factors of Sex among elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District of West Bengal is retained.

Table-4

Mean difference between Male and Female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal on their Responsiveness of Rules and Regulations, dimension of Professional Quality

Gender	N	MEAN	SD	SEM	df	t	p-value
Male	110	103.29	10.972	1.046			
Female	90	103.03	10.427	1.099	198	0.169	0.798
Total	200						

Note. level of significance 0.05.

The results presented in Table-4 show the comparison of scores on Dimension-1 (Responsiveness to Rules and Regulations) between male and female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District. The mean scores of male and female teachers are almost identical, indicating very similar levels of responsiveness towards rules and regulations. Thus, both male and female teachers exhibit comparable levels of responsiveness to institutional rules and regulations. Therefore, gender does not appear to have any significant influence on teachers' responsiveness to rules and regulations among the elementary school teachers in West Bengal. Hence, the hypothesis stating that 'There is no significance difference of Responsiveness of Rules and Regulations, dimension of Professional Quality based on demographic factors of Sex among elementary school teachers in Alipurduar District of West Bengal is retained.

Table-5

Mean difference between Male and Female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal on their Planning and Preparation of Organizational Work, dimension of Professional Quality

Gender	N	MEAN	SD	SEM	df	t	p-value
Male	110	76.42	9.919	0.946			
Female	90	77.69	7.815	0.824	198	0.990	0.060
Total	200						

Note. level of significance 0.05.

The results presented in Table-5 show the comparison of scores on Dimension-2, Planning and Preparation of Organisational Work between male and female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District. The mean score of male teachers is very close to that of female teachers. The result shows that there is no statistically significant difference in Planning and Preparation of Organizational Work, dimension of professional quality between male and female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal. Thus, both male and female teachers demonstrate similar levels of professional quality in planning and preparing of organisational work. Hence, the hypothesis stating that 'There is no significance difference of Planning and Preparation of Organizational Work, dimension of Professional Quality based on demographic factors of Sex among elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District in West Bengal is retained.

Table-6

Mean difference between Male and Female elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal on their Mastery over the understanding of teaching technique, dimension of Professional Quality

Gender	N	MEAN	SD	SEM	df	t	p-value
Male	110	78.85	10.241	0.976			
Female	90	78.87	10.403	1.097	198	.008	0.677
Total	200						

Note. level of significance 0.05.

The results presented in Table-4 show the comparison of male and female elementary school teachers on Mastery over the understanding of teaching technique, dimension of professional quality. The result show that there is no significant difference between male and female elementary school teachers in their Mastery over the understanding of teaching technique. Thus, both male and female demonstrate similar levels of Mastery over the understanding of teaching technique. Hence, the hypothesis stating that 'There is no significance difference of Mastery over the understanding of teaching technique, dimension of Professional Quality based on demographic factors of Sex among elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District in West Bengal is retained.

Table-7

Mean difference between Urban and Rural elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal on their Professional Quality

Area	N	MEAN	SD	SEM	df	t	p-value
Rural	110	257.436	26.861	2.561			
Urban	90	262.477	23.427	2.469	198	1.398	0.495
Total	200						

Note. level of significance 0.05.

The results presented in Table-7 show the comparison of total Professional Quality scores between urban and rural elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District in West Bengal. The result show that there is no statistically significant difference in the professional quality of urban and rural elementary school teachers of Alipurduar district in West Bengal. Therefore, the hypothesis stating that "There is no significance difference of Professional Quality based on demographic factors of Locale among elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District in West Bengal is retained.

Objective-3: To examine the influence of teaching experience on professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District in West Bengal.

Table-8

Teaching Experience based on ANOVA

Teaching Experience	N	df	F-value	p-value
≤10 Years	80	Between = 1		
>10 Years	120	Within = 198	10.529	.001
Total	200	Total =199		

Note: Significant at 0.01 level

The results presented in Table-8 show the influence of teaching experience on professional quality of elementary school teachers of Alipurduar District in West Bengal. This result show that teaching experience has a significant influence on professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar district in West Bengal. Therefore, teachers with more than 10 years of teaching experience differ significantly in their professional quality levels compared to teachers with below 10 years of teaching experience. Hence, the hypothesis stating that ‘There is no significance influence of teaching experience on professional quality of elementary school teacher of Alipurduar District of West Bengal’ is rejected.

V. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Present study found that 53.5% of teachers exhibit high professional quality, while 39% show moderate professional quality. Only 4.5% demonstrate very high professional quality, and a small fraction (3%) fall into the low professional quality. The study also found that among male teachers, 54.55% exhibit high professional quality, 39.09% moderate, 2.73% very high, and 3.64% low Professional Quality. Among female teachers, 52.22% show high professional quality, 38.89% moderate, 6.67% very high, and 2.22% low Professional Quality. Regarding location, 56.67% of urban teachers have high professional quality, 38.89% moderate, 3.33% very high, and 1.11% low Professional Quality. Among rural teachers, 50.91% show high professional quality, 39.09% moderate, 5.45% very high, 4.55% low professional quality. These findings align with Sharma & Sharma (2021), who found that most primary school teachers fall within moderate to high professional quality levels due to structured teacher training programs and experience-based skill development. Similarly, Gupta (2020) found that continuous professional development positively influences teaching competency and quality.

The study found no statistically significant difference in professional quality scores between male and female teachers. This result aligns Kaur & Verma (2019), who found that gender does not significantly impact teaching competency, as both male and female teachers receive similar training and professional exposure. However, Das & Mukherjee (2022) observed slight variations in teaching styles but concluded that these differences do not translate into significant disparities in teaching effectiveness. This aligns with research by Sharma & Singh (2020), who found that gender does not significantly affect teaching competency, emphasizing that professional quality is more influenced by training and experience rather than gender.

Present study found no significant difference between urban and rural teachers regarding professional quality. This finding contrasts with Patel & Singh (2018), who noted disparities due to resource availability and exposure to advanced pedagogical tools. However, Reddy (2021) argues that modern teacher training programs and digital interventions have minimized such differences and making location less influential on teacher quality. Similar findings were reported by Patel & Reddy (2018), who noted that infrastructural differences between urban and rural schools did not translate into disparities in teachers’ professional quality, as individual teacher motivation played a larger role.

Present study significantly found that teachers with above 10 years of teaching experience perform significantly better than those with below 10 years of teaching experience. This aligns with Saxena (2020), who found that teaching experience correlates positively with professional quality, as experienced teachers tend to develop better classroom management and instructional skills. Similar findings by Bose & Nair (2019) suggest that years of experience contribute to improved lesson planning, adaptability, and student engagement. Similarly, Kumar et al. (2019), who concluded that professional competency grows with years of experience, as experienced teachers develop better planning skills and adaptive teaching strategies.

Objective: To provide recommendations for teacher training programs and policy interventions to enhance Professional Quality.

V.I. STRUCTURED AND EXPERIENCE-BASED TRAINING PROGRAMS

Structured and experience-based training programs should be implemented to address the diverse needs of teachers at different career stages. For teachers with below 10 years of experience, the focus should be on strengthening pedagogical skills, enhancing student engagement, and integrating technology into the classroom. For those with above 10 years of teaching experience should emphasize innovation, leadership development, and strategies to prevent professional stagnation. To maintain continuous

professional growth, regular refresher courses should be mandated. To ensuring that experienced teachers stay updated with evolving teaching methodologies. Additionally, rural-urban bridging programs should be introduced to foster knowledge exchange between teachers from different regions, helping to bridge gaps in teaching quality and promote equitable education for all students.

V.II. COLLABORATION AND MENTORING PROGRAMS

To foster a culture of continuous learning and collaboration, reverse mentoring programs should be introduced, pairing experienced teachers with younger, tech-savvy educators to exchange best practices on technology-enhanced teaching. Establishing Professional Learning Communities (PLCs) can further strengthen this approach by creating collaborative peer groups where teachers share innovative teaching techniques, classroom strategies, and experiences. To motivate participation, recognition and incentive schemes should be implemented, rewarding teachers who actively engage in peer learning and mentorship. This holistic approach not only enhances professional growth but also cultivates a supportive and dynamic teaching community.

V.III. PERIODIC CAREER ADVANCEMENT OPPORTUNITIES

To support teachers' professional growth and well-being, periodic career advancement opportunities should be introduced, including mid-career skill enhancement programs focused on educational leadership and subject mastery. Work-life balance interventions are equally essential, offering psychosocial support, workload management training, and stress reduction programs to prevent burnout and maintain job satisfaction. Additionally, performance-based recognition systems should be implemented, linking professionalism and dedication to career growth, financial incentives, and public acknowledgment. This comprehensive approach not only motivates teachers to strive for excellence but also ensures their personal and professional well-being, fostering a more resilient and committed teaching workforce.

V.IV. PRIORITIZE INNOVATION

Teacher evaluation metrics should be redefined to prioritize innovation and impact over tenure, focusing on the adoption of creative teaching methods rather than solely considering years of experience. Student engagement and learning outcomes should serve as key performance indicators, reflecting the effectiveness of classroom practices. To support this shift, monitoring and feedback mechanisms must be strengthened through regular classroom observations and structured teacher self-reflections, fostering a culture of continuous improvement. Additionally, policies should be developed to promote technology integration in teaching, ensuring that both young and experienced educators are equipped with the skills to apply modern pedagogies effectively. This holistic approach not only enhances teaching quality but also drives meaningful professional growth.

VI. CONCLUSION

The study affirms that professional quality of primary school teachers in Alipurduar remains predominantly high, ongoing professional development programs are essential for sustaining and enhancing teacher professional Quality. Experience emerges as a dominance force to determine professional quality of Primary School Teacher, whereas gender and locale exert minimal influence. Thus, a nuanced and dynamic approach to teacher training rooted in experience, collaboration, and innovation. It is an indispensable for cultivating a resilient and high-performing teaching workforce. The insights derived from this study have practical implications for policymakers and educational stakeholders. This study gives data-driven foundation for crafting strategic interventions aimed at improved teacher quality and advancing equitable education systems.

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